

OpenMod Africa

Standalone and open documentation for the suite of models

Deliverable No. 3.3

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List of Abbreviations

EV	Electric Vehicle
GENeSYS-MOD	The Global Energy System Model
GIS	Geographic Information System
OM4A	Open Modelling toolbox For Africa
PV	Photovoltaic
RES	Renewable Energy System
SSV	Seasonal Storage Valuation

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Executive Summary

The Horizon Europe Energy project 101118123 – OpenMod4Africa (Open Modelling Toolbox for development of long-term pathways for the energy system in Africa) is a three-year project (2023–2026) about the development of an energy modelling toolbox for analyses of the future energy and power systems in Africa. Furthermore, capacity building in the use of models and further development of the toolbox, among African experts, is a core element in the project.

The main objective is to contribute to an improved and robust understanding of how to develop an energy and a power supply to all Africans by making available, demonstrating and using an open modelling Toolbox. The OM4A Toolbox is populated with a suite of open, integrated, state-of-the-art models and a common database including all necessary data for conducting, among others, scenario building exercises at regional and national level. Two case studies are being conducted to demonstrate the use of the Toolbox, and in addition provide new insights into important challenges related to the energy transition. The research in the project is done in dialogue with three stakeholder groups, one in the Eastern African Power Pool region, one in the Western African Power Pool region, and one in Tunisia.

In this deliverable, we focus on how the models and their documentation are made accessible with training material to African Stakeholders for conducting energy system transition studies in Africa.

The OM4A Toolbox includes the 6 following models:

- GENeSYS-MOD, which analyses long-term low-carbon energy transition pathways considering all energy sectors: electricity, buildings, industry, and transport;
- openTEPES, a decision support system for defining the integrated generation, storage, and transmission expansion plan of a large-scale electric system;
- plan4res, a power system model, which includes a capacity expansion module (adaptation of the generation and storage mix as well as of the existing interconnections in a given year), focused on the optimization of the strategies for managing seasonal storages, and the simulation of the system operation. plan4res focuses on electricity;
- InfraFair, which determines the network utilisation by agents (demand and generators using the network) and countries and, associated with this, the allocation of the cost of the network among agents or countries;
- OnSSET, a Geographic Information Systems (GIS) based tool that enhances electrification planning and decision-making for the accomplishment of energy access goals in currently unserved areas;
- EV-PV, whose goal is to support electric mobility planning, with a focus on predicting the spatio-temporal charging needs, the number of required charging stations, and the potential for PV energy to cover the charging demand. The model focuses on private passenger mobility. Within the framework of the project, a second model has been developed to also address public transport electrification.

This report, Deliverable D3.3, builds upon Deliverable D3.2 by detailing how the suite of linked and open-source models -adapted to the African context- along with their associated training materials and documentation, have been made available online. The goal is to enable new users to independently access and apply the OpenMod4Africa toolbox in their own case studies.

1 Introduction

The Horizon Europe Energy project 101118123 – OpenMod4Africa (Open Modelling Toolbox for development of long-term pathways for the energy system in Africa) is a three-year project (2023–2026) about the development of an energy modelling toolbox for analyses of the future energy and power systems in Africa. Furthermore, capacity building among African experts in use and development of the toolbox is a core element in the project.

The main objective is to contribute to an improved and robust understanding of how to develop an energy and a power supply to all Africans by making available, demonstrating and using an open modelling Toolbox. The Toolbox is populated with a suite of open integrated state-of-the-art models and a common database including all necessary data for conducting, among others, scenario building exercises at regional and national level. Two case studies are demonstrating the use of the Toolbox, and in addition providing new insights into important challenges related to the energy transition. The research in the project is done in dialogue with two stakeholder groups, one in the Eastern African Power Pool region and one in the Western African Power Pool region.

The overall objective of WP3, ‘Model development and adaptation’ is expanding the functionalities and adapting the features of the models within the Toolbox developed in WP4, so that they can adequately represent the transition of the energy systems in Africa towards secure, affordable, and clean energy for all. The specific objectives to be pursued related to the former are listed next:

1. Design and implementation of the integration of additional open-source models into the Toolbox.
2. Development of detailed specifications of the upgrades that the models should undergo.
3. Implementation of the upgrades to the models previously specified.

This deliverable aims at completing Objective 3, via Task 3.3 ‘Development of the extensions of the open-source models.’

In chapter 2, we introduce the OM4A open energy system modelling toolbox, which includes the suite of linked and open-source models available to the public as well as the training material and documentation. We mainly discuss the following:

- How to access and navigate the OM4A open energy system modelling toolbox, to access models, tools and training materials on <https://africaenergymodels.net>.
- The GitHub accounts for the models and what information they contain to allow for an easy user experience.
- The GitHub organization for all training materials as part of OM4A and how they can be accessed and utilized by the users to enable a faster and easier learning experience.

2 The OM4A Toolbox

This chapter introduces and explains the OM4A open energy system modelling toolbox, which can be accessed via <https://africaenergymodels.net/>. The open energy modelling toolbox contains all models, installation and

user guides, as well as information on the case studies conducted in OM4A to test the modelling toolbox. It incorporates also a page to visualize the results from the case studies, and a link to the Permanent network site aiming to enable the development of a community of African energy modelling experts and stakeholders within and beyond the OM4A Project.

2.1 How the repository works

<https://africaenergymodels.net/> is a comprehensive platform dedicated to advancing energy system modelling across the African continent. It is specifically designed to support researchers and practitioners in developing robust, data-driven energy strategies that are aligned with Africa's unique development priorities and sustainability goals.

This website facilitates the use of energy models that reflect the continent's diverse geographic, economic, and social contexts. By offering access to open-source tools, high-quality datasets, and opportunities for collaboration, <https://africaenergymodels.net/> empowers its users to analyse and plan effective, sustainable energy transitions. The energy system modelling efforts conducted through the platform consider critical factors such as rapid population growth, expanding economic activities, infrastructure development, and the urgent need to address climate change.

In doing so, the platform serves, not only as a technical resource hub, but also as a catalyst for building local capacity and fostering regional cooperation in the energy modelling community across Africa.

Its general structure is explained below:

Figure 1: African Energy Models main page

The main page when accessing <https://africaenergymodels.net/> enables the users to navigate between multiple subpages (see Figure 1 that will be explained in the following):

Models

On the Models subpage, users are presented with an overview of all the models available in the OM4A Open Energy System Modelling Toolbox. Through provided links, users can access individual pages for each model, which offer more detailed information as well as links to the respective GitHub repositories where the models can be accessed to be installed and used. Additional information about the GitHub pages is provided in Section 2.2 of this report.

Data

The Data page provides users with detailed information on the standardized variable template and nomenclature package used across the OM4A Toolbox. These resources define a consistent structure for variables, regions, and units used in energy system models, supporting transparency, interoperability, and collaboration across modelling teams.

On this subpage, users can find:

- An explanation of the variable template: A shared list of variables with hierarchical naming conventions that follow international standards, designed for clarity and compatibility across models.
- Region definitions: A structured classification of geographic areas, from global and regional aggregates to individual countries and sub-national regions (e.g., NUTS levels and e-highway2050 clusters).
- Details on directional data: Guidelines for representing flows between regions (e.g., Senegal>Guinea).
- Access to tools and packages: Links to GitHub repositories hosting YAML files and a Python package for validating and processing scenario data.
- Licensing and contribution info: The resources are open-source and available for use and contributions by the wider modelling community.
- The page also provides links to the GitHub repository and documentation, allowing users to download the template, explore the code, and adopt or extend the nomenclature in their own modelling work.

Case Studies

The Case Studies subpage provides an overview of how the OM4A Toolbox is being used in real-world applications across Africa, featuring summaries that demonstrate its capacity to support energy planning and policy development. It serves as a practical reference for researchers, policymakers, and practitioners interested in how the toolbox is applied to address Africa's energy challenges.

On this subpage, users find detailed descriptions of the regional case studies in West Africa and East Africa—including the objectives, leading institutions, geographic focus, and key themes considered. This page outlines the scope of each study, such as mini-grids, electrification, and national and regional energy system analyses. It also highlights how the toolbox supports both technical insights and capacity building in local contexts.

Training

The Training subpage provides links for users to access training materials for all the models available in the OM4A Toolbox, hosted under <https://github.com/OM4A-Training-Material>. This GitHub organization contains individual repositories for each model, offering a wide range of resources to support users in effectively working with the models. More details about the GitHub organization are provided in Section 2.3 of the report. Furthermore, YouTube links are provided that enable the users to explore the main functionalities of the model (Installation, how to run the model etc.).

Visualisation

The Visualisation subpage offers an interactive way to explore the scenarios and case studies from the OM4A Toolbox. At the centre of the page is a map-based tool that allows users to visually engage with the geographic and model-based data.

Users can browse available case studies and scenarios directly on the map, gaining insights into how the OM4A models can be applied to different regions across the continent. For a more detailed and immersive experience, the page includes a button linking to the full version of the visualisation tool on its dedicated platform. This enables deeper exploration of data, model outputs, and regional energy system dynamics in an intuitive and user-friendly format.

Permanent Network

Link to the webpage of the African Energy Modelling Network (<https://africanenergymodellingnetwork.net/>), which highlights its core activities, including training, research support, and capacity building, and emphasizes its role in fostering innovation and providing evidence-based insights for policy and planning. It also presents

the network's broader goal of enabling a just and sustainable energy transition by connecting academia, industry, and policymakers.

2.2 GitHub – Accessing the models

GitHub is a powerful platform for sharing models and training materials due to its accessibility, collaboration features, and version control capabilities. It allows users to easily download, modify, and contribute to open-source projects, fostering a collaborative development environment. Since all the models were already using GitHub, it was decided that this project would continue to use GitHub repositories to ensure a uniform and simplified experience for users working with different models and tools. To ensure each GitHub repository is easy to use, informative, and consistent with the experience provided by the GitHub pages of other models, we defined several best practice guidelines that all repositories should follow. However, there is some flexibility for the modelling teams in how they implement these guidelines and in the final design of their GitHub pages. Some main sections the GitHub repository for a model should include follow:

Readme

The Readme is the entry point of the repository, giving users an immediate overview of the model and its purpose. It outlines what the repository contains, who it's for, and how it fits within the broader project. A clear Readme helps users quickly understand whether the model is relevant to their needs and provides direction on where to go next. Without it, users may struggle to navigate or engage with the content.

Introduction / Overview / Features

This section provides a concise explanation of what the model does, its intended applications, and its main features. It helps users determine whether the model fits their research or policy context. By clearly defining the model scope and purpose, it avoids misuse and sets realistic expectations about what the model can deliver.

Installation / Quick-Start / Usage

Installation instructions guide users through setting up the model, including any software dependencies. A quick-start or usage guide allows them to test the model shortly after setup, confirming that everything works correctly. This section is essential for lowering the barrier to entry and encouraging broader use of the model.

Example Data / Tutorial

Example datasets and tutorials offer practical demonstrations of how to run the model. They show users what inputs are needed, what outputs to expect, and how to interpret results. These materials are key for learning, troubleshooting, and applying the model to real-world scenarios.

Contact

The contact section provides a way for users to reach out with questions, feedback, or contributions. It may include contributor names, emails, or links to support platforms. Having a clear contact point supports collaboration, and ensures users are not left without help when needed.

Following the definition of best practices, each model's GitHub page was reviewed during online meetings with all modelling teams present. During these sessions, the content and structure of each repository were examined to ensure alignment with the agreed guidelines. Where needed, model pages were updated to address gaps or improve clarity. This collaborative process ensured consistency across repositories while allowing for input and adjustments from each team. Table 1 provides an overview of all the models, includes links to their respective GitHub pages, and demonstrates that all the model repositories now adhere to established best practices.

Table 1: GitHub best practice

	GENeSYS-MOD	openTEPES	InfraFair	EV-PV	plan4res	OnSSET
Link	https://github.com/GENeSYS-MOD	https://github.com/IIT-EnergySystemModels/openTEPES	https://github.com/IIT-EnergySystemModels/InfraFair	https://github.com/evpv-simulator	https://github.com/plan4res	https://github.com/OnSSET
Readme	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Introduction/Overview/Features	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Installation/Quick-Start/Usage	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Example Data/Tutorial	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Contact	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes

2.3 GitHub Organization - Accessing the learning material

We have created a GitHub Organization to provide centralized access to all the training materials for each model on one platform. A GitHub Organization is a shared account that allows multiple users to collaborate on a collection of repositories. This setup is ideal for managing educational resources, especially when multiple contributors are involved in developing and maintaining content. The primary purpose of this GitHub organization is to provide accessible, structured, and reusable training content that supports African stakeholders in learning how to use and adapt the OM4A energy system modelling tools.

By organizing the training materials under one GitHub Organization, we ensure that users can easily find, access, and interact with the resources for different models. The organization structure also supports role-based access control, enabling team members (such as model developers, trainers, and reviewers) to have appropriate permissions for managing repositories. Version control ensures that all changes are tracked and managed transparently, allowing for reliable updates and consistent documentation. The Permanent Network will ensure that the Organization will be updated and maintained beyond the OM4A project. The main page for the GitHub organization can be seen in Figure 2. The homepage of the organization introduces users to the overall training platform through a clear and informative README file. This serves as an entry point for new users, outlining the purpose of the platform, its relevance to African stakeholders, and how the training materials support scenario-based energy planning at national and regional levels. It also provides links to the YouTube channel (<https://www.youtube.com/@africanenergymodellingnetwork>), containing videos to further support the training material and enable users' easy installation and use of models.

Figure 2: GitHub Organization OM4A Training Material

Each model within the toolbox: GENeSYS-MOD, OpenTEPES, plan4res, OnSSET, InfraFair, and EV-PV has its own dedicated repository (see Figure 3). These repositories contain the relevant training materials, examples, and documentation specific to each tool, making it easier for users to navigate and access resources tailored to the model they are using. Each repository within the organization contains model-specific content, including code, documentation, and tutorials. Users can download the materials, suggest improvements, and contribute updates through GitHub's collaborative features.

Figure 3: GitHub Organization – Model Repositories

Finally, the organization is also designed to evolve over time. New training content and tutorials will be progressively added to meet the needs of African researchers, planners, and institutions. By centralizing these materials under one organizational structure, users benefit from a unified and consistent experience, while also gaining access to broader networks such as the African Energy Modelling Network. In addition, a Q&A repository has been set up within the organization, providing users with a collection of questions related to each of the models that arose during the project. This allows users to find answers to common questions quickly and efficiently.

3 Conclusion

The activities carried out under Task 3.3 have successfully led to the implementation of the model extensions. For deliverable D3.3, a strong emphasis was placed on accessibility and usability. All the models have been documented and made available through a centralized online repository (<https://africanenergymodels.net>), with clear guidance for installation, operation, and linkage. Training materials have also been developed and shared (<https://github.com/OM4A-Training-Material>) to support the African stakeholders in applying the Toolbox in their own regional and national planning exercises.

This deliverable together with deliverable D3.2 not only completes the technical implementation of the model extensions as outlined in Task 3.3 but also lays the foundation for broader dissemination and long-term capacity building efforts. The continued engagement with regional stakeholders and the accessibility of the tools ensure that OpenMod4Africa can contribute meaningfully to sustainable and inclusive energy transitions across the continent.